

Compressibility Studies in Aqueous Electrolytes

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Ultrasonic velocities and their variation with concentration have been measured for aqueous electrolytes of various valence types at 25°. The experimental adiabatic compressibilities of solutions obtained from velocity measurements are compared with those calculated on the basis of simple additivity law making appropriate corrections for hydrated water. The agreement between the experimental and calculated compressibilities is satisfactory.

The changes in hydration number with concentration as calculated using Barnartt's formula have been attributed to water layers intermediate between the incompressible first shell and the bulk water.

Robinson and Stokes¹ have developed an activity coefficient formula on the basis of assumed hydration of ions. The provisions introduced for the ion-hydration alter the significance of the mole fractions. These authors assume that every ion in solution is hydrated and a fixed number of water molecules is rigidly bound to the central ion at all dilutions. These bonded water molecules become a part of the ion and thus are withdrawn from the free solvent, with the result that the effective concentrations of the electrolyte increase appreciably. The activity coefficients calculated by the proposed formula on the basis of assumed hydration are in agreement with experimental data up to the saturation concentration in the case of uni-univalent and bi-univalent electrolytes.

In the present paper, we have calculated the compressibilities of aqueous electrolyte solutions (β_{12} calculated) by simple additivity law, on the assumption that the electrolyte with its hydrated water has zero compressibility.

The compressibility of the solution is given by the additivity law

$$\beta_{12} = f_1\beta_1 + f_2\beta_2 \quad (1)$$

where β_{12} is the calculated compressibility of solution, β_1 and f_1 are the compressibility and mole fraction of free solvent, β_2 and f_2 are the compressibility and mole fraction of solute with the hydrated water. The solute with the bound solvent has zero compressibility ($\beta_2 = 0$)

$$\therefore \beta_{12} = f_1 \times \beta_1 \quad (2)$$

EXPERIMENTAL

The measurements of ultrasonic velocity were carried out by Hiedemann and Bachem's secondary interference method at a frequency of 2.1 M.C./s and 25°, with an accuracy of ± 1 m/s.

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1. R. A. Robinson and R. H. Stokes, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1870.

The experimental adiabatic compressibilities are calculated from velocity data by Newton's formula

$$\beta_{12} = \frac{1}{U^2 d} \quad (3)$$

β_{12} = Experimental adiabatic compressibility of solution in sq.cm./dyne.

U = velocity in cms/sec.

d = density in gms. ml.

The experimental compressibility data for solutions are tabulated in column (4).

The hydration numbers of electrolytes (n) calculated from the experimental compressibility data using the Barnartt² equation are tabulated in column (7).

$$n = \frac{n_1}{n_2} \left[1 - \frac{\beta_{12} V}{\beta_1 n_1 V_1^0} \right] \quad (4)$$

n = hydration number of the electrolyte.

V = volume of solution containing n_1 moles of water and n_2 moles of electrolyte.

V_1^0 = molal volume of pure water

β_{12} = observed compressibility of solution.

β_1 = observed compressibility of water.

Method of Calculations : To calculate β_{12} for 4M NaCl solution.

From the density of 4M NaCl, 1000 ml of it weighs 1148.4 gms, and contains 233.8 gm NaCl. Therefore 914.6 gm. of water are present in 1000 ml of 4M NaCl solution. Therefore 50.81 moles of water are present in 4M NaCl solution, out of which 40 moles of water are bound to ions as hydrated water (as each molecule of NaCl has ten molecules of bound water) and 10.81 moles of water are existing as free solvent.

$$\begin{aligned} \therefore \text{Mole fraction of free water } (f_1) &= \frac{\text{Moles of free water}}{(\text{Moles of free water} + \text{Moles of solute})} \\ &= \frac{10.81}{10.81 + 4.0} \\ &= 0.7298 \end{aligned}$$

$\therefore$ Using equation (2) and the compressibility of water

$$\begin{aligned} \beta_{12} \text{ calculated} &= 0.7298 \times 44.93 \times 10^{-12} \\ &= 32.77 \times 10^{-12} \end{aligned}$$

These calculated values of compressibilities of solutions are tabulated in column (5).

TABLE 1

NaCl

<i>C</i> Molarity	<i>U</i> m/s	<i>d</i> gm/cc.	$\beta_{12} \times 10^{12}$ cm ² /dyne		<i>n</i>	
			Experimental	Calculated (Author)	Author	Barnartt
0.0	1494	0.9971	44.93	44.93	—	—
0.5	1523	1.0174	42.42	44.48	10	5.20
1.0	1555	1.0371	39.89	43.93	10	5.18
1.5	1584	1.0564	37.73	43.25	10	4.86
2.0	1612	1.0752	35.79	42.37	10	4.55
2.5	1645	1.0941	33.83	41.19	10	4.38
3.0	1671	1.1124	32.20	39.55	10	4.12
3.5	1699	1.1305	30.64	37.03	10	3.90
4.0	1722	1.1484	29.38	32.77	10	3.64

TABLE 2

KCl

Molarity	<i>U</i> m/s	<i>d</i> gm/cc.	$\beta_{12} \times 10^{12}$ cm ² /dyne		<i>n</i>	
			Experimental	Calculated (Author)	Author	Barnartt
0.0	1494	0.9971	44.93	44.93	—	—
1.0	1543	1.0427	40.29	43.89	11	4.11
2.0	1593	1.0870	36.25	42.13	11	3.70
3.0	1634	1.1292	33.18	38.29	11	3.13
3.5	1658	1.1507	31.61	34.02	11	2.987

TABLE 3

HCl. (Data Ref. 3)

<i>C</i> Molarity	<i>U</i> m/s	<i>d</i> gm/cc.	$\beta_{12} \times 10^{12}$ cm ² /dyne		<i>n</i>	
			Experimental	Calculated (Author)	Authors	Barnartt
0.0	1497	0.997	44.72	44.72	—	—
1.92	1550	1.062	39.20	42.99	4	3.40
2.32	1543	1.075	39.06	42.57	4	2.85
3.33	1539	1.105	38.22	41.39	4	2.18
4.80	1509	1.150	39.21	39.31	4	1.42

TABLE 4

C Molarity	U m/s	d gm/cc.	$\beta_{12} \times 10^{12}$ cm ² /dyne		Author	n Barnartt
			Experimental	Calculated (Author)		
0	1494	0.9971	44.93	44.93	—	—
0.5	1507	1.0130	43.48	44.49	4	0.86
1	1521	1.0283	42.05	44.01	4	0.84
2	1552	1.0588	39.20	42.87	4	0.80
3	1586	1.0888	36.49	41.39	4	0.72
4	1617	1.1175	34.27	39.36	4	0.51
5	1650	1.1470	32.02	36.44	4	0.40

TABLE 5

C Molarity	U m/s	d gm/cc.	$\beta_{12} \times 10^{12}$ cm ² /dyne		Author	n Barnartt
			Experimental	Calculated (Author)		
0	1494	0.9971	44.93	44.93	—	—
0.5	1511	1.0054	43.57	44.50	4	1.30
1	1537	1.0132	41.79	44.02	4	1.78
2	1569	1.0282	39.53	42.93	4	1.21
3	1604	1.0421	37.31	41.56	4	0.99
4	1635	1.0555	35.46	39.76	4	0.75
5	1662	1.0681	33.91	37.31	4	0.53

TABLE 6

C Molarity	U m/s	d gm/cc.	$\beta_{12} \times 10^{12}$ cm ² /dyne		Author	n Barnartt
			Experimental	Calculated (Author)		
0	1494	0.9971	44.93	44.93	—	—
0.25	1482	1.0324	44.11	44.73	7	2.44
0.50	1478	1.0680	42.87	44.49	7	3.52
0.75	1472	1.1028	41.84	44.25	7	3.53
1.50	1459	1.2066	38.92	43.38	7	3.26
3.00	1450	1.4117	33.68	40.72	7	2.86
4.00	1450	1.5458	30.76	37.47	7	2.55
5.00	1449	1.6805	28.35	31.02	7	2.24

TABLE 7

<i>C</i> Molarity	<i>U</i> m/s	<i>d</i> gm/cc.	$\beta_{12} \times 10^{12}$ cm ² /dyne		<i>n</i>	
			Experimental	Calculated (Author)	Author	Barnartt
0	1494	0.9971	44.93	44.93	—	—
0.3	1469	1.0946	42.30	44.65	16	6.96
0.6	1451	1.1913	39.88	44.31	16	6.45
0.9	1440	1.2883	37.42	43.87	16	6.36
1.2	1433	1.3841	35.19	43.27	16	6.02
1.5	1427	1.4802	33.18	42.40	16	5.65

TABLE 8

<i>C</i> Molarity	<i>U</i> m/s	<i>d</i> gm/cc.	$\beta_{12} \times 10^{12}$ cm ² /dyne		<i>n</i>	
			Experimental	Calculated (Author)	Author	Barnartt
0	1494	0.9971	44.93	44.93	—	—
0.1	1499	1.0154	43.84	44.84	16	11.99
0.3	1505	1.0512	42.02	44.63	16	10.40
0.5	1523	1.0870	39.66	44.45	16	11.40
0.7	1532	1.1221	37.96	44.21	16	10.62
1.0	1552	1.1744	35.36	43.76	16	10.07

TABLE 9

<i>C</i> Molarity	<i>U</i> m/s	<i>d</i> gm/cc.	$\beta_{12} \times 10^{12}$ cm ² /dyne		<i>n</i>	
			Experimental	Calculated (Author)	Author	Barnartt
0	1494	0.9971	44.93	44.93	—	—
0.3	1517	1.0251	42.39	44.66	16	9.77
0.6	1543	1.0521	39.95	44.34	16	9.47
0.9	1567	1.0777	37.77	43.94	16	8.94
1.2	1593	1.1037	35.70	43.44	16	8.57
1.5	1614	1.1283	34.04	42.79	16	7.96

TABLE 10
 $MgCl_2$ (Data Ref. 4 at 30°)

C Molarity	U m/s	d gm/cc.	$\beta_{12} \times 10^{12}$ cm ² /dyne		n	
			Experimental	Calculated (Author ¹)	Author	Barnartt
0	1510.0	0.9956	44.052	44.052	—	—
0.1	1520.9	1.0030	43.102	43.97	11	10.7
0.2	1531.7	1.0112	42.152	43.86	11	10.9
0.4	1552.3	1.0265	40.429	43.71	11	10.37
0.8	1595.8	1.0564	37.172	43.30	11	9.72
1.0	1617.1	1.0712	35.699	43.06	11	9.38
2.0	1714.1	1.1417	29.811	41.37	11	7.70
4.0	1877.4	1.2724	22.298	25.51	11	5.37

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Hydration numbers of electrolytes: From the tables it is seen that the hydration number of an electrolyte calculated using Barnartt's equation decreases with increase in concentration and afterwards levels off to a nearly constant limiting value.

Equation (4) is proposed for calculating the hydration numbers of electrolytes on the assumption that the ion and the primary hydration shell is incompressible and the rest of the solution possesses a compressibility equal to that of pure water.

In reality between the incompressible first shell and the normal bulk of water, there is a region wherein (due to the gradually decreasing ionic influence), there are water molecules having compressibility intermediate between that of extremes. This intermediate water structure can be thought to extend up to the thickness of ionic atmosphere which is more in dilute region than in concentrated region⁵. Equation (4) does not recognize this intermediate category of water in solution, which in effect adds to the value of primary hydration numbers. The effective contribution of this intermediate water structure to the primary hydration should therefore go on decreasing with increasing concentration becoming negligible after a certain limit. Thus the variations in primary hydration number result because of our inability to account for this intermediate structure.

Experimental and calculated compressibilities of solutions: The experimental compressibilities of solutions are linear up to a concentration of 3 moles for uni-univalent and 1.5 moles for other valence type electrolytes.

3. P. Prozorov, *J. Phys. Chem.*, U.S.S.R., 1940, **14**, 384.

4. Weissler and Del Grosso, *J. Acou. Soc. Am.*, 1951, **23**, 219.

5. H. S. Harned and B. B. Owen, *Physical Chemistry*, Reinhold Publication, II Edition, p. 33.

The values of hydration numbers by Barnartt's equation vary with the concentration but we have calculated the compressibilities assuming a constant hydration number throughout the entire concentration. These assumed hydration numbers are tabulated in column 6. The agreement between the experimental and calculated compressibilities of solutions is satisfactory for uni-univalent electrolytes. The discrepancy in the case of electrolytes of higher valence type is attributed to their complex behaviour.

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